

Cultural Barriers to Communicative Learning in ESL Class

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Abstract:

Teachers of ESL, teaching English texts are familiar with a feeling that their utterances are going to waste as they neither get the expected feedback nor non-verbal response from their learners. In such a situation there is a danger of lowering expectations and falling in a downward spiral of simplifying language further, using direct questions that elicit close ended responses and thus decreasing the chances of conversational exchanges.

A thorough understanding of the expectations of L₂ learners, their needs, motivation and interactive competence while keeping their socio-cultural framework in view is needed.

This paper advocates the use of texts that have authentic materials involving naturally occurring language as a means of communication rather than those texts that have native speaker contexts which may be alien to the speakers of other languages. It presents a few cultural barriers that impede communicative learning.

INTRODUCTION

Methodology and content play a major role in the paradigm of ELT. Studies related to educational implicature of contrastive rhetoric recommend that all users of English must learn the preferred models of rhetoric as it is a desirable component of ELT. But as Rubin puts it, “voiceless, genderless, identity-less prose is the most desirable.”¹

Awareness of broader perspectives of the use of English as appropriate to Outer Circle has been missing so far. A wider perspective to study the relevant needs

in the field of English education in the outer and expanding circle is called for. Though it is an acceptable justification “to raise the consciousness of the English educators”² about the preferred rhetorical patterns of the L₁ countries, it is perfectly legitimate and necessary to raise consciousness about different rhetorical styles of learners of English. “Just as no language is more or less logical than another, no rhetorical pattern is more or less logical.”³ As conventions differ culturally and all have to live together in the present global village, educating the international users of the texts to be sensitive to the expectations of the outer circle readers is as desirable as educating the readers to be sensitive of the inner circle English users. The responsibility is to be equally shared to make out the meaning of the texts as human history proves the fact that no cultural tradition was intimidated by the scholarship of other traditions. An openness towards cultural scholarships of other countries enriches the linguistic structures and the rhetorical styles. Creative literature has come of age and multicultural, multilingual writers like Keri Hulme (Booker Prize winner of Britain 1985), Raja Rao (The Neustadt Prize of the United States) and Wole Soyinka from Niger and Derek Walcott from Trinidad (Nobel Prize Winner for Literature) have won major English literary prizes. Fostering cross-cultural, universal understanding by appreciating the cultural differences is the ideal of education and language teaching can take a lead in this exercise.

Materials authentic to the location are a valuable source of language teaching that may include articles from newspapers and magazines, advertisements, recipes etc. Since they are not beneficial to all the levels of learners, the next best option is to design texts which are for the non-native learners. These texts with lived cultural content and social context increase learners’ motivation for learning, reinforce the real language and provide authentic cultural information. Learners relate closely to their own cultural material as it addresses their need to communicate effectively in their social and personal transactions. These texts will also help learners to be creative, increasing their curiosity and adding to a sense of identification. One’s own culture as a content in the language classroom also strengthens the values, customs, beliefs, art and traditions of the L₂

countries by transmission through the English texts. Learners own culture as a content for English language learning in the formative years is compatible with the recent acceptance of the existence and practice of English in the expanding circle as a formidable force in the emerging English paradigm.

Countries like India and China will have vast majority of people who will have relatively less and less face-to-face interaction with the native speakers. If this is the foreseeable future, then, the Euro-Christian cultural content in the English language texts does not help in the language learning process. This content may prove to be detrimental in shaping the consciousness of the learners. The feeling of in-betweenness experienced by the learners in learning a foreign culture through a foreign language hinders the learning process. To assume that foreign culture must play a major role since it is inherent in the foreign language reflects a failure to realize the situation in reality. This assumption reveals a monolingual inability to grasp the complexity of multilingual and multicultural societies.

There are several broad solutions to the issues discussed above. This paper presents a few barriers like culture, classroom management, learner expectations and learner behaviour. The learning of second language invariably entails the readjustment of linguistic and cultural systems to a certain degree. These readjustments require an understanding of the worldview of the L₂ community which in turn depends on the range of differences between the L₁ and L₂ of the learners.

Lawrence F. Bouton's investigation into learning of meanings in conversational implicature and L₂ interactions points out that culturally defined context of communication and the role of interactants define the learner's interpretation of the conversational implicature. It also points out that, members from different cultures seem to have different ideas about their roles in an interaction. It can be noted that non-native speakers of English can acquire lexical and conceptual efficiency but second culture acquisition, that entails rhetorical styles, continues to be missing. This leads to the conclusion that second culture acquisition is not

the conceivable aim of second language learning.⁴ The cultural barriers that impede communicative learning are presented below.

Limitations of Communicative Learning Tasks

The analysis of ELT methodology reveals that achieving communicative competence in a second language involves not only knowing the grammatical rules of a language but also knowing when, where and with whom to use the language in a contextually appropriate way. This requires more than mere knowledge of English grammar and vocabulary; it requires skill in how to use English language in communicative situations.⁵ Some limitations in communicative learning tasks are given below.

Limitations of the Classroom Management

The principles of CLT are not always easy to put into practice. For instance, large class sizes tend to favour receptive activities involving reading and listening because they are less demanding and time-consuming for the teacher than productive activities involving speaking and writing in pairs or groups. The result is teacher-centered instruction that does not provide students with critical unrehearsed language practice and individual attention.

Limitations of Learner Expectations

Another hurdle maybe, the fact that learners feel too shy or embarrassed to interact or participate in the class. This cultural inclination is in fact a type of performance anxiety that learners from L₂ countries often suffer from while learning English. In cultures like India where teacher-centric teaching is the norm, it may not be easy for the learners to respond readily to the communicative tasks. Teachers may be disappointed with the reluctance of the learners in this context where, it is considered a virtue and a sign of respect to listen to elder people and only speak when asked to. The teacher is placed in a position of reverence and “Guru Devo Bhava” is practised.

Learner centeredness prescribes forms of democratic student collaboration which might not be appropriate in all classroom, professional, academic and student cultures.⁶

Limitations of the Learners Behaviour

Indian students consider the textbooks as an authority. The teacher is expected to explain the text while the students learn from listening attentively as the teacher is considered a dispenser of knowledge. Though they accept the text book knowledge uncritically, they are constantly on their own to decipher the conversational implicature and interactional context. The students hesitate to express their thoughts as their cultural background consists of the notion that no one can really contribute anything new unless one has achieved mastery over a given field or any relevant technique. When they participate, they reflect carefully to ensure that the point they raise is valid and pertinent. Their concern for social relationships, like respect for fellow students, for teachers, group harmony and belongingness towards community are variant to the assumed perceptions of the L₁ writers of the curriculum. The questions related to the alien cultural content in the textbook may seem a formidable task for the learners to answer. Many of the students are afraid that seeking clarifications on the unknown or unclear points in the text may invite ridicule from the peers; so the learners wait for the explanations. It is the teacher who must predict the possible questions that may arise from the learners in the classroom and make provision at the stage of lesson planning. This demands an ability to predict and decide the type of hurdles the learners may face and calls for an approach that balances the learner expectations and the teaching aims. Even if the teacher puts in effort to explain the cultural context of the prescribed lesson or text, it is not totally helpful in the language learning context for an ESL learner.

Conclusion

As McKay asserts, the key to a balanced approach in the English language instruction is “to be culturally sensitive to the diversity of contexts in which English is taught and used.”⁷

The variety being taught must be based on the context, cultural needs and educational needs of the learners. The teachers' own abilities and the teaching styles need to align with the socially accepted norms. With the variable in teaching contexts, there seems to be no single choice that can be assumed to be correct for all contexts.

Finally it is for the teachers to work out the model that is based on context of their social group and needs of their learners. Resultantly the decision may be different for every teacher.

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